

INTERACTIVE METHODS OF INCREASING PUPILS' VOCABULARY IN ENGLISH LESSONS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7370112>

Annotation: This article is about the methods used to increase the vocabulary of pupils in English lessons. An important task is to teach students to think independently in English classes. We know that in the current educational process, the learner must be a subject. One of the most important requirements for lessons is to teach students to think independently. Keywords: English, lesson, interactive methods, reader, vocabulary, methods, word, education system.

During the years of independence, Uzbekistan has undergone great changes. This is especially evident in the education system. Because the education system has a task to bring up a free-thinking, well-rounded, mature person. To do this, we teachers need to effectively use new methods in the classroom. The experience of developed countries in the world is based on advanced pedagogical technologies, the knowledge of students not only satisfying their interest and needs, but also high also solves the task of training qualified specialists.

State policy in the field of personnel training makes a person intellectual and spirituality is a continuum that is inextricably linked with moral upbringing through the education system to form a comprehensively developed person - a citizen. In this way, knowledge of the most basic constitutional rights of the citizen is to demonstrate his creative ability. To the requirements of the Law on Education and the National Training Program so we organize the lessons in a non-traditional way, not in a traditional way will be needed. We teachers have to do a lot of research to do that Among the world languages, English has a special place. This is an international language It has become a means of communication on a global scale, now all over the world English is spoken in the regions. It is developed in countries such as the United Kingdom, the United States, Canada and Australia received the status of the state language. It is special to learn English in our country attention is paid. Our ancestors were well versed in foreign languages and made world-class discoveries in the history of science and culture. We must teach young people to master foreign languages, worthy of the spirit of our generations. Requirements of the Law on Education and the National Training Program so we

organize the lessons in a non-traditional way, not in a traditional way will be needed. We, as teachers, have to do a lot of research. English has a special place among the world's languages. It is an international language. It has become a means of communication on a global scale, now all over the world. English is spoken in the regions. It is developed in countries such as the United Kingdom, the United States, Canada and Australia received the status of the state language. It is special to learn English in our country attention is paid. Our ancestors were well versed in foreign languages and made world-class discoveries in the history of science and culture. We must teach young people to master foreign languages, worthy of the spirit of our generations. The use of different games in solving this problem is a positive result will give. When words are taught through games, students quickly learn new words and these words will remain in their memory for a lifetime. Such games with the whole class, or in small groups can be taught. Let's see what games they can use: 1. Memory game. One student one. The other student adds a word or phrase to the sentence. Student 1: My friend came. Student 2: My friend and his mother came.

Student 3: My friend and his mother came by train. Which student adds a word If he fails or makes a mistake, he leaves the game. 2. Word association. A word from a class is taken. For example: Words about home appliances. Student 1: a Sofa. Student 2: a table. Student 3: a chair. Student 4: the piano. Any student who can't find a word quickly leaves the game. 3. Miming. This game is designed for high school students who need to know a lot of words, that is, have a rich vocabulary. This game can be professional. The beginner acts on a profession, the rest have to find out what profession the word belongs to, otherwise they may ask: Do you work with children? Do you work in the evening? 4. Guess the tool. The teacher divides the students into pairs. 2 students face to face and give them cards with words. For example: Knife and cook, pen and pupil. These students should not show the note to each other. Students must describe the word without saying the name of the tool on the card. Another has to find the same tool: Student 1: It is used for cutting things (bread, vegetables). Student 2: It is a knife. We use it to prepare meals. 5. Finding words through human voices (Human sounds) In this game, students learn when people are happy, when they are sad, when they are sick. learn how to make sounds. Teacher: You are at the concert, at the stage. Reader: Sings and says I am singing. Teacher: Someone is here... Student: Whispers something and says I am whispering. Teacher: You hurt your leg. Reader: Screams and says I am screaming. At the end of the game, students can find, say, and perform similar actions on their own. 6. Suggestion

chain. In this game, students make an offer to spend their free time. To do this, each of them writes down this evening or tomorrow afternoon or weekend, and then one of them starts the game. The other students also express their opinions: Student 1: Let's go to the football match. 2-student: No, not football. What about going to the concert? Student 3: We could go to the concert. Student 4: No, not to the concert. Why don't we visit the country? The game continues in this order. All students must be able to make suggestions. Anyone who fails to make a correct sentence or repeats the same verb in the sentence will be expelled.

7. Notices and warming practices The teacher prepares two types of cards. The first type of card contains phrases and sentences that are said in some places. The second type is to say the same words and phrases on the cards possible locations are displayed. For example: Student 1: Many students are reading books. 2-reader: In the library. Student 3: Tickets are sold out. Student 4: Out side of the theater. Student 5: Queue for currency exchange. Student 6: Inside a bank.

8. Exaggerate This method allows students to choose different qualities. for this The teacher prepares cards with different types of questions: It isn't very interestig, is it? She is very pretty, isn't she? Did you have a good day? The cards are placed on the table. The teacher calls one of the students, takes one of the cards and orders him to read the question. This student asks the other student to answer the question using the adjectives. Student 1: She cooked nice meals, didn't she? Azim? Student 2: (Azim) Nice? She cooked delicious. Whoever fails to use the attributes appropriately or makes a mistake is considered a loser. 9. Expand the sentences This game also applies to adjectives, and several adjectives must be used in sentences: Teacher: He ate an apple. Student 1: He ate a red apple. Student 2: He ate a red big apple. 10. Game using Synonyms. In this game, the teacher says a word and the teachers find synonyms for that word. The student who can find the most synonyms is the winner: Teacher: Ability. Student 1: talent. Student 2: skill. Student 3: aptitude. Teacher: business. Student 1: industry Student 2: commerce Student 3: trade Student 4: Traffic 11. Tests in checking students' vocabulary we can use: For example: Jane: Where are... going, Ann? a) you b) he c) she d) it Ann: I'm just going to the.... a) office b) shops c) post office d) hospital Jane could you... this letter with you? a) take b) give c) post d) buy Ann: With pleasure.

These types of games help students of all ages to increase their English vocabulary. English teachers can make the game conditions easier or more

difficult, taking into account the age characteristics and level of knowledge of English learners. In short, these games are the level of children or we can also make it easier or harder depending on our age. The purpose of interactive games is different We can summarize, increase vocabulary, speed, intelligence, and most importantly, learn the lesson in an interesting way and remember it.

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